

Operational Guide for Tumor-LN-oC platform

Tumor-LN-oC proposes the development and validation of a TRL 5 tumor-lymph node-on-chip platform composed of 3D tissue models and microfluidic chips which will connect surgically removed human primary tumors and lymph node tissue (LN) from the same lung cancer patient. This will serve as a “biological twin” of the patient and will allow Tumor-LN-oC consortium to study the interaction of primary tumors with LNs for individual patients.

To this aim, a high-level flowchart of the platform’s operation during the experimental runs is shown in Figure 1. Each action is color-coded to match its respective component-level module. A detailed guide regarding the process’ steps can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Operational guide of the platform.

Step #	Action
1	Prepare cell lines for printing.
2	Initialize equipment and controllers of the platform. Specifically: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Power on computer• Power on MIP spectroscopy module• Power on microfluidic module• Power on temperature and humidity controllers and select temperature and humidity level.• Power on translation stage and CCD cameras
3	Laser printing of cells inside the chip’s chambers.
4	Set media flow rate and feed the chip
5	Power on recirculatory flow module
6	Live imaging of the chips’ microchannels.
7	Acquisition of MIP spectra
8	At the end of the experiment, the chips will be emptied of media and cells and will be cleaned via ethanol/isopropanol.

Platform modules	
	Laser printing
	Software & control
	Microfluidic peripherals
	live imaging
	MIP spectroscopy

Figure 1. Platform operation flow chart.